

Kinetics and mechanism of iridium(III) catalysed oxidation of DL-methionine by alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III)

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Abstract : Iridium(III) catalysed oxidation of DL-methionine by hexacyanoferrate(III) was studied spectrophotometrically in aqueous alkaline medium at 30 ± 0.1 °C at a constant ionic strength. A micro amount of iridium(III) was sufficient to catalyse the slow reaction between DL-methionine and hexacyanoferrate(III). The reaction is first order in both hexacyanoferrate(III) and iridium(III) concentrations. The order with respect to DL-methionine is fractional. Increase in the alkali concentration increases the reaction rate. Methionine sulfone was found to be the main product of oxidation and it was identified by IR and mass spectra. Hexacyanoferrate(II), the other product was found to have no effect on reaction rate. The active species of oxidant and catalyst are $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-}$ and $[\text{IrCl}_3(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2\text{OH}]^-$ respectively. A possible mechanism was proposed and the activation parameters were computed with respect to the slow step of the reaction.

Keywords : Oxidation of DL-methionine, hexacyanoferrate(III), iridium(III), mechanism.

Introduction

Methionine, cysteine and cystine are the three sulphur containing amino acids and are the constituents of proteins. The metabolism of sulphur is vital for all living organisms and methionine is one of the essential amino acids, which must be supplied through diet. It has three reaction sites S, O and N out of which sulphur is more reactive. So far very few kinetic studies have been reported on the oxidation of methionine in alkaline medium using various oxidants¹⁻⁷. Hence we have extended our studies on the oxidation of methionine.

Hexacyanoferrate(III), $[\text{HCF}(\text{III})]$ is a well known one electron oxidant and the oxidation of amino acids using $\text{HCF}(\text{III})$ in alkaline medium⁸⁻¹¹ has received much attention presumably due to its less complexity involved in mechanistic elucidations. Iridium(III) is reported to be an efficient catalyst for such oxidations in alkaline medium¹²⁻¹⁵. The uncatalysed reaction between DL-methionine and $\text{HCF}(\text{III})$ in alkaline medium was reported previously at 55 °C by Laloo and Mahendra². Recently we have reported the ruthenium(III) catalysed oxidation of DL-methionine by $\text{HCF}(\text{III})$ in alkaline medium⁷, wherein the rate decreased with increase in $[\text{methionine}]$. Since the

reaction between methionine and $\text{HCF}(\text{III})$ was also found to be catalysed by iridium(III), the title reaction was undertaken with a view of elucidating the mechanism.

Results and discussion

Stoichiometry and product analysis :

The reaction mixtures containing excess $[\text{HCF}(\text{III})]$ over $[\text{methionine}]$ in presence of iridium(III) in 0.3 mol dm^{-3} alkali were allowed to react at 30 ± 0.1 °C. After 24 h, the residual $[\text{HCF}(\text{III})]$ in each case was determined spectrophotometrically at 420 nm. The results obtained indicated that four moles of $\text{HCF}(\text{III})$ was consumed by one mole of methionine and the product was identified as methionine sulfone. The stoichiometry of the reaction was found to correspond to the equation :

The reaction product was isolated by solvent extraction method using an organic solvent, diethyl ether and it was identified by its IR spectrum (Fig. 1), which showed the bands (ν) at 1152.64 and 1394.32 cm^{-1} corresponding to

Fig. 1. IR spectrum of methionine sulfone.

O=S=O stretching, the band (ν) at 1655 cm^{-1} due to -COOH stretching and a broad band (ν) at 3223 cm^{-1} corresponds -NH stretching respectively. The positions of the absorption bands for sulfone were found to be in good agreement with the literature values of symmetric and asymmetric SO_2 stretching frequency.

Further, the reaction product was confirmed by mass spectral studies (Fig. 2). The mass spectrum shows a peak at m/z 184 which was very close to the literature value of the oxidation product methionine sulphone. Basing on these observations the product of oxidation of methionine by alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III) in presence of iridium(III) was confirmed to be methionine sulphone.

Fig. 2. Mass spectrum of methionine sulfone.

Effect of ionic strength :

The effect of ionic strength was studied by maintaining ionic strength using NaClO_4 solution from $0.40\text{--}0.90\text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. The pseudo-first order rate constants obtained from \log (absorbance) versus time plots were found to remain constant, thus indicating that the ionic strength had no significant effect on the rate of the reaction (Table 1).

Effect of [hexacyanoferrate(II)] :

The $[\text{HCF(III)}]$, $[\text{methionine}]$, $[\text{iridium(III)}]$ and $[\text{OH}^-]$ were kept constant in order to examine the effect of concentration of hexacyanoferrate(II), one of the products, on the rate of reaction. It was observed that the constancy of rate constants obtained from the slopes of pseudo-first order plots, showed that $[\text{hexacyanoferrate(II)}]$ did not have any effect on the reaction rate (Table 1).

Effect of [oxidant], [substrate], [alkali] and [iridium(III)] :

The order with respect to HCF(III) was determined by carrying out the kinetic runs in 0.3 mol dm^{-3} sodium hydroxide in presence of $2.0 \times 10^{-2}\text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ methionine, $4.0 \times 10^{-6}\text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ iridium(III), 0.4 mol dm^{-3} ionic strength (μ) and varying the concentration of HCF(III)

over the $1.0\text{--}6.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ range. The plots of log (absorbance) versus time were found to be linear indicating the order with respect to [HCF(III)] is unity and the data was listed in Table 1. The rate dependence on

[methionine] was investigated by varying the concentration of methionine in the range of $1.0\text{--}6.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ at three different temperatures 25, 30 and 35 °C keeping the concentrations of all other reactants constant. The pseudo-first order rate constants, k' were found to be increased with increase in [methionine] (Table 2) and the order with respect [methionine] was found to be fractional. Also the plots of $1/k'$ versus $1/[\text{methionine}]$ were found to be straight lines with positive intercepts on the rate axis (Fig. 3) indicating that the reaction obeys Michael-

Table 1. Effect of [HCF(III)], [Ir^{III}] and ionic strength (μ) on the pseudo-first order rate constant (k') at 30 ± 0.1 °C

$[\text{Met}] = 2.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{OH}^-] = 0.3 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$

[HCF(III)] $\times 10^4$ (mol dm ⁻³)	[Ir ^{III}] $\times 10^6$ (mol dm ⁻³)	μ (mol dm ⁻³)	$k' \times 10^4$ (s ⁻¹)
1.0	4.0	0.4	6.52
2.0	4.0	0.4	6.32
3.0	4.0	0.4	6.38
4.0	4.0	0.4	6.44
5.0	4.0	0.4	6.48
6.0	4.0	0.4	6.52
4.0	2.0	0.4	3.07
4.0	3.0	0.4	4.60
4.0	4.0	0.4	6.54
4.0	5.0	0.4	8.06
4.0	6.0	0.4	9.60
4.0	7.0	0.4	11.13
4.0	4.0	0.4	6.52
4.0	4.0	0.5	6.41
4.0	4.0	0.6	6.45
4.0	4.0	0.7	6.48
4.0	4.0	0.8	6.40
4.0	4.0	0.9	6.39

Table 2. Effect of [Met] and [OH⁻] on the pseudo-first order rate constant (k') at 298, 303 and 308 K

$[\text{HCF(III)}] = 4.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}] = 4.0 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$

[Met] $\times 10^2$ (mol dm ⁻³)	[OH ⁻] (mol dm ⁻³)	μ (mol dm ⁻³)	$k' \times 10^4$ (s ⁻¹)		
			298 K	303 K	308 K
1.0	0.30	0.40	3.05	4.80	7.67
2.0	0.30	0.40	4.57	6.44	9.97
3.0	0.30	0.40	5.34	7.15	10.74
4.0	0.30	0.40	5.95	7.67	11.89
5.0	0.30	0.40	6.73	8.12	12.66
6.0	0.30	0.40	7.12	9.21	13.15
2.0	0.10	0.70	2.43	3.84	6.45
2.0	0.20	0.70	3.28	5.18	7.89
2.0	0.30	0.70	4.60	6.50	9.21
2.0	0.40	0.70	5.47	6.98	9.70
2.0	0.50	0.70	6.68	7.65	10.66
2.0	0.60	0.70	8.27	8.30	11.38

Fig. 3. Plot of $1/k'$ versus $1/[\text{Methionine}]$.

lis-Menten type of kinetics. To understand the influence of the [hydroxide ion] on the rate of the reaction kinetic runs were carried out at three different temperatures 25, 30 and 35 °C by varying the [alkali], keeping the concentrations of all other reactants constant. The pseudo-first order rate constants, k' values obtained were found to be increased with increase in $[\text{OH}^-]$ (Table 2) and the order with respect to $[\text{OH}^-]$ is fractional. Further, the plots of $1/k'$ versus $1/[\text{OH}^-]$ were found to be straight

lines with positive intercepts on the Y-axis (Fig. 4). To know the order with respect to [iridium(III)] on the reaction rate, [iridium(III)] was varied in the range of $2.0\text{--}7.0 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ by keeping the concentrations of all other reactants constant. The plot of k' versus $[\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}]$ (Fig. 5) was found to be a straight line passing through the origin indicating unit order dependence on $[\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}]$ (Table 1).

Fig. 4. Plot of $1/k'$ versus $1/[\text{OH}^-]$.

Fig. 5. Plot of $1/k'$ versus $[\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}]$.

Test for free radicals :

The test for free radicals was carried out by taking methionine, sodium hydroxide and iridium(III) in a thumberg tube and acrylonitrile and hexacyanoferrate(III) in the bent tube. After evacuating the system the solutions were mixed by tilting the tube. The reaction mixture was kept aside and even after 24 h no precipitate was observed indicating the absence of free radicals.

Discussion

Methionine exists as zwitter ion in aqueous solutions. In the present kinetic study ($[\text{OH}^-] = 0.3 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) 99% of methionine exists as anionic species, $\text{H}_3\text{CSCCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}(\text{NH}_2)\text{COO}^-$ (Met) and which is presumed to be the reactive species.

Hexacyanoferrate(III) is an octahedral inner orbital complex and acts as one electron oxidant. There are very few reports of catalysis by iridium(III) in alkaline medium and the nature of iridium(III) species in aqueous alkaline solutions is not well understood. It is a d^6 metal ion and adopts low spin t_{2g}^6 arrangement with relatively high ligand field strengths prevailing in these complexes of $4d^n$, tripositive transition series metal ions. It exists in the form of an octahedral complex, $[\text{IrCl}_6]^{3-}$, in hydrochloric acid medium which on aquation forms several species like $[\text{Ir}(\text{H}_2\text{O})\text{Cl}_5]^{2-}$, $[\text{Ir}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2\text{Cl}_4]^-$ and $[\text{Ir}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3\text{Cl}_3]$. In view of the increase in rate with increase in $[\text{OH}^-]$, $[\text{IrCl}_3(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2\text{OH}]^-$ is considered to be the active form of iridium(III)¹⁵ and basing on these observations the following mechanism was proposed.

Mechanism :

where, $\text{R} = -\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}(\text{NH}_2)\text{COO}^-$

$$\therefore \text{Rate} = \frac{-d[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}]}{dt} = k[\text{C}][\text{HCF(III)}] \quad (4)$$

$$= kK_2[\text{Met}]_e[\text{IrCl}_3(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2\text{OH}]_e[\text{HCF(III)}] \\ = kK_1K_2[\text{Met}]_e[\text{IrCl}_3(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3]_e[\text{OH}^-]_e[\text{HCF(III)}] \quad (5)$$

where, $[\text{Met}]_e = [\text{Met}]_t$ and

since,

$$[\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}]_t = [\text{IrCl}_3(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3]_e + [\text{IrCl}_3(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2\text{OH}]_e + [\text{C}]_e \quad (6)$$

and

$$K_1 = \frac{[\text{IrCl}_3(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2\text{OH}]_e}{[\text{IrCl}_3(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3]_e[\text{OH}^-]}$$

Therefore,

$$[\text{IrCl}_3(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3]_e = \frac{[\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}]_t}{1 + K_1[\text{OH}^-] + K_1K_2[\text{Met}]_t[\text{OH}^-]} \quad (7)$$

Substituting for $[\text{IrCl}_3(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3]_e$ from eq. (7) in eq. (5) gives

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{kK_1K_2[\text{Met}]_t[\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}]_t[\text{HCF(III)}][\text{OH}^-]}{1 + K_1[\text{OH}^-] + K_1K_2[\text{Met}]_t[\text{OH}^-]} \quad (8)$$

The above rate equation explains the first order dependence on $[\text{HCF(III)}]$ and $[\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}]$, fractional order with respect to $[\text{OH}^-]$ and increase in rate with increase in [methionine].

$$\text{Since, } \frac{\text{Rate}}{[\text{HCF(III)}]} = k^1 \\ = \frac{kK_1K_2[\text{Met}]_t[\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}]_t[\text{OH}^-]}{1 + K_1[\text{OH}^-] + K_1K_2[\text{Met}]_t[\text{OH}^-]} \quad (9)$$

Taking reciprocals on both sides, it leads to

$$\frac{1}{k_1} = \frac{1}{kK_1K_2[\text{Met}]_t[\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}]_t[\text{OH}^-]} + \frac{1}{kK_2[\text{Met}]_t[\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}]} + \frac{1}{k[\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}]_t} \quad (10)$$

The above equation predict the plots of $1/k'$ versus $1/[\text{methionine}]$ and $1/k'$ versus $1/[\text{OH}^-]$ should be straight lines with positive intercepts on Y-axis. Exactly similar plots were obtained experimentally (Figs. 4 and 5) thus

supporting the proposed mechanism.

From the plot of $1/k'$ versus $1/[\text{methionine}]$, the intercept and slope are $1/k[\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}]_t$ and $1/kK_1K_2[\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}][\text{OH}^-] + 1/kK_2[\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}]$ respectively.

Further, the rate constants of the rate-determining step, k and equilibrium constants, K_1 and K_2 were determined from the slopes and intercepts of these plots and are presented in Table 3. Substituting these values in the rate law, the rate constants were calculated and compared with the experimental values. They were found to be in good agreement with each other (Table 4). The activation parameters of the rate-determining step, E_a and ΔS^\ddagger , were computed using linear least squares method and are found

Table 3. Rate constants of the rate determining step

$[\text{HCF(III)}] = 4 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}] = 4 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$

Temp. (K)	k ($\text{mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$)	K_1 ($\text{mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3$)	K_2 ($\text{mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3$)
298	192.30	0.23	866.66
303	229.35	0.60	605.55
308	337.84	1.53	336.36

Table 4. A comparison of observed and calculated values of pseudo-first order rate constant, k'

$[\text{HCF(III)}] = 4 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}] = 4 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$,
 $[\text{OH}^-] = 0.3 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $\mu = 0.4 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $t = 30 \pm 0.1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$

$[\text{Met}] \times 10^2$ (mol dm^{-3})	$k' \times 10^4$ (s^{-1})	
	Obsd.	Calcd.
1.0	4.80	4.40
2.0	6.44	5.95
3.0	7.15	6.74
4.0	7.67	7.24
5.0	8.12	7.54
6.0	9.21	7.77

to be $42.41 \pm 2.85 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ and $-208.10 \pm 9.41 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ respectively. From the critical examination of the nature of the species and the conditions employed for the reaction, the following points may be put forth in support of the proposed intimate mechanism.

- (i) In the presence of hydroxide ion, $[\text{IrCl}_3(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3]$ is converted to $[\text{IrCl}_3(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2\text{OH}]^-$ with the replacement of H_2O molecule but not to $[\text{Ir}(\text{Cl})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3\text{OH}]$ by means of the exchange of Cl^- . This is supported by the experimental observation that chloride ion did not have any in-

hibitory effect on the reaction rate.

- (ii) The more the CFSE of a species, the higher will be the activation energy needed for the reaction. H_2O exhibits more crystal field stabilization energy compared to OH^- and hence it occurs high in the spectrochemical series. According to this $[\text{IrCl}_3(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3]$ has high CFSE compared to $[\text{IrCl}_3(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2\text{OH}]^-$ and hence the latter is presumed to be the reactive species of iridium(III).
- (iii) Further, $[\text{IrCl}_3(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2\text{OH}]^-$ reacts with the anionic species of methionine to form a negatively charged complex (C) through the formation of Ir-S bond which can be supported by the fact that the late transition metals in the groups to the right of the periodic table are soft and have high affinity towards sulphur than oxygen.
- (iv) The attack of substrate on the $[\text{IrCl}_3(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2\text{OH}]^-$ species is facilitated because of less steric hindrance of $[\text{IrCl}_3(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2\text{OH}]^-$ compared to $[\text{IrCl}_3(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3]$. As such the steric effect facilitates a fast reaction between the substrate and $[\text{IrCl}_3(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2\text{OH}]^-$.
- (v) The iridium(III)-substrate complex (C) reacts with HCF(III) with the occurrence of outer sphere electron transfer between the complex (C) and HCF(III) to give positively charged sulphur species of the substrate, Ir^{III} and HCF(II).
- (vi) Further, the positively charged sulphur species of methionine will be oxidized by HCF(III) to form methionine sulphone in several fast steps.

These arguments are in support of the following intimate mechanism proposed for this reaction.

Intimate mechanism :

where R = -CH₂CH₂CH(NH₂)COO⁻

Experimental

Materials and reagents :

DL-Methionine in 0.1 mol dm⁻³ NaOH was prepared afresh by dissolving the sample in a requisite volume of sodium hydroxide and its strength checked iodometrically¹⁶. Hexacyanoferrate(III) (E. Merck) was prepared by dissolving the requisite amount of potassium hexacyanoferrate(III) in double distilled water. The solution was standardised by measuring its absorbance at 420 nm ($\epsilon = 1060 \pm 50 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$). Iridium(III) solution was prepared by dissolving iridium chloride in 2.0 mol dm⁻³ hydrochloric acid (Johnson Matthey, London) and its strength was determined¹⁷. Sodium hydroxide (E. Merck) solution was prepared and standardised by potassium hydrogen phthalate.

Procedure and kinetic measurements :

All kinetic measurements were performed under pseudo-first order conditions with $[\text{OH}^-] > [\text{DL-methionine}] > [\text{HCF(III)}] \gg [\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}]$ at constant ionic strength. The reaction was initiated by mixing thermally equilibrated solution of HCF(III) to a mixture solution of DL-methionine, iridium(III) and sodium hydroxide at 30.0 ± 0.1 °C. The reaction was followed by measuring the absorbance of HCF(III) at 420 nm using Milton Roy

Spectronic-1201 UV-Visible spectrophotometer. The pseudo-first order rate constants, k' were determined from the slopes of log (absorbance) versus time plots. The plots were linear up to 85% completion of the reaction and the rate constants were found to be reproducible within ± 3 .

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